

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02

Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

D5.2: Communication and Dissemination Activities Report – First Period

Lead partner: WavEC Offshore Renewables

Authors: Janete Gonçalves, WavEC Offshore Renewables

Reviewer: Paola Zerilli, UoY

Submission date: 31/10/2023

Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
17-10-2023	V1	Janete Gonçalves / First Draft
17-10-2023	V1.1	Flaminia Rocca and Riccardo Coletta / review
19-10-2023	V2	Janete Gonçalves / Second Draft
24-10-2023	V2.1	Paola Zerilli / scientific review
27-10-2023	V2.2	Flaminia Rocca and Riccardo Coletta / final review

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
TABLE OF FIGURES.....	4
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
2 INTRODUCTION	6
3 BRAND IDENTITY – LOGO AND TEMPLATES.....	6
4 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	7
4.1 WEBSITE	7
4.2 SOCIAL MEDIA.....	8
4.3 FLYER, ROLL-UP, DOCUMENT HOLDERS AND MERCHANDISING	9
4.4 MULTIMEDIA MATERIAL	10
4.5 PRESS RELEASES	10
4.6 REPRESENTATION AT RELEVANT STAKEHOLDER PLATFORMS AND CONFERENCES	11
4.7 MARINEWIND Co-CREATION WORKSHOPS	12
4.7.1 EVENT PLANNING	16
4.7.2 ARTICLES IN NEWSPAPERS.....	16
4.7.3 PERFORMANCE INDICATOR LOG	16
5 CONCLUSIONS	17
ANNEX I – PERFORMANCE INDICATOR LOG	18

TABLE OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1 - MARINEWIND logo - colour and black & white version</i>	6
<i>Figure 2 - MARINEWIND logo Pantone codes</i>	6
<i>Figure 3 - MARINEWIND Deliverables and PowerPoint Presentations templates.....</i>	7
<i>Figure 4 - Website homepage banner</i>	8
<i>Figure 5 - LinkedIn and Twitter/X example posts</i>	9
<i>Figure 6 - Flyer, Roll-up, Document holders and Merchandising.....</i>	9
<i>Figure 7 – Graphical study of the first MARINEWIND video.</i>	10
<i>Figure 8 - Inès Tunga (CATAPULT) at WindEurope Annual Event announcement.</i>	11
<i>Figure 9 - Inès Tunga (CATAPULT) presenting MARINEWIND during the event "ASK 4 Green".</i>	12
<i>Figure 10 - EMD 2023 - In My Country - logo of the initiative</i>	13
<i>Figure 11 – The Italian 1st Co-creation workshop in Bari.....</i>	14
<i>Figure 12 – The Italian 1st Co-creation workshop in Bari: participants overview.</i>	14
<i>Figure 13 – The UK 1ST Co-creation workshop in Aberdeen</i>	15
<i>Figure 14 – The Greek 1st Co-creation workshop</i>	15
<i>Figure 15 – The Spanish 1st Co-creation workshop.....</i>	15

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable D5.2, the Communication and Dissemination Activities Report for the First Period, is a pivotal component of Task 5.2, within work package 5 of the MARINEWIND project. This task is dedicated to the effective communication of project activities and findings to a wide-ranging audience, ensuring that the project's impact extends beyond its conclusion. D5.2 encapsulates all partner activities that transpired during the initial project phase.

The establishment of a distinctive brand identity marked the project's inception, including recognizable project logo and templates. These visual elements are essential for cohesive and professional project representation across various media, both traditional and online.

To reach diverse audiences, during its initial period (M1-12), the MARINEWIND project has leveraged a spectrum of communication and dissemination channels and tools. The aforementioned include the project website, active social media engagement, promotional materials, press releases, and participation in conferences and events.

The project website, launched in March 2023, serves as the primary information hub for MARINEWIND, offering comprehensive insights into the project's objectives, activities, and consortium partners respective roles. It has collected 498 users and 4,800 total event counts, with users from all around the world, underpinning its role as a vital communication tool.

Social media platforms, namely LinkedIn and Twitter/X, were initiated in January 2023, enhancing outreach efforts, and providing a dynamic space for stakeholders to stay updated and engage with project developments.

To boost visibility and promote the project in the context of both external events and conferences, promotional materials, including flyers, roll-up banners, document holders, and merchandising items, were created.

The project also unveiled itself to the public through a press release, disseminated in July 2023, which emphasized the potential of Floating Offshore Wind Energy Technologies. Furthermore, consortium partners actively participated in conferences, such as the WindEurope Annual Event, and organised co-creation workshops, such as "Co-creation Path to Awareness on Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)" in Bari, Italy, and the "Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind" workshop in Aberdeen, UK, which was a side event to the "Floating Offshore Wind 2023" conference. These events were instrumental in connecting and networking with key stakeholders, disseminating project achievements, and addressing inquiries.

2 INTRODUCTION

The deliverable D5.2 - Communication and Dissemination Activities Report – First Period is produced under the aim of Task 5.2 – Communication and Dissemination Activities (M1-36). Therefore, D5.2 will present all the partners' communication and dissemination activities that took place during the First Period of the project.

3 BRAND IDENTITY – LOGO AND TEMPLATES

A recognizable visual identity has been designed by WAVEC as C&D leader at the initial stage of the project (M1). The following *Figure 1* presents the project Logo, both in colour and black & white version. *Figure 2* displays the pantone codes, which graphic companies may require for printing materials.

Figure 1 - MARINEWIND logo - colour and black & white version

Figure 2 - MARINEWIND logo Pantone codes

To enhance project recognition, WAVEC have developed dedicated Word and PowerPoint templates for partners to use, respectively, in reference to the MARINEWIND deliverables and slideshow presentations. These templates are presented below, in Figure 3.

- Activities (Information about the several work packages of the project).
- Reports (Deliverables and other non-confidential information about the project will be available there).
- Partners (Short information about the partners, logos, and link to website).
- News & Events (Diverse information about the project's activities, events, and other useful information).
- Contacts (Contact form for those who would like to contact the Consortium).
- The project website will foresee a specific section to host the WebGIS (Geographic Information System) tool (D4.1, led by RSE).

The website is linked to Google Analytics to track the number of visitors, the duration of the visit, the locations and the devices used for browsing it, as well as other useful information.

Since its start and until the end of September – 30/09/2023-, the website counted with 498 users and, for an insight about users' behaviour and engagement, 4,800 total event counts. Most of the visitors came from Italy (87), followed by UK (60), USA (58), Portugal (57), and Spain (34).

The website has been regularly updated with news about the project activities.

Figure 4 - Website homepage banner

4.2 Social Media

In addition to other dissemination channels, MARINEWIND utilizes social media platforms, specifically LinkedIn and Twitter/X, to convey its findings to the intended audiences. The LinkedIn page is accessible at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/marinewind>. This LinkedIn page has currently 104 followers.

The MARINEWIND project also has a presence on Twitter/X, which can be accessed at https://twitter.com/marinewind_eu. This Twitter/X page has currently 16 followers.

These social media platforms provide an additional avenue for the project to engage with its audiences, share updates and information, and increase the visibility and the recognition of the project.

Both platforms were initiated on January 2, 2023 (M4).

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of the project, D5.1, presents more information about the social media platforms and hashtags to be used by partners in their posts.

Figure 5 - LinkedIn and Twitter/X example posts

4.3 Flyer, ROLL-UP, Document holders and Merchandising

To enhance visibility and advance the promotion of the MARINEWIND project during conferences and exhibitions, promotional materials, such as a flyer, a roll-up banner, document holders and merchandising material, were created in the project's early stages. These materials serve as valuable instruments for promoting the project and increasing awareness among potential stakeholders and the general public.

Figure 6 - Flyer, Roll-up, Document holders and Merchandising

4.4 Multimedia Material

The MARINEWIND Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.1, developed by the lead partner WAVEC) outlines the creation of a project promotional video, initially scheduled for completion by Month 12. The content of the video has been reviewed, and the design team has presented their graphic design concepts to both the coordinator APRE and WAVEC. They are currently in the process of producing this initial video.

Figure 7 – Graphical study of the first MARINEWIND video.

4.5 Press releases

At the outset of the MARINEWIND project, the Consortium disseminated a press release on the 14th of July 2023, in order to introduce the initiative to the public.

The main topics of this Press Release include the MARINEWIND project's objectives to accelerate the adoption of Floating Offshore Wind Technology (FOWT) in Europe. These objectives encompass enhancing social acceptance through evidence-based tools, increasing awareness of FOWTs potential, supporting investments, analysing barriers and opportunities for commercialization, exploring environmental impacts, creating jobs in the FOWT sector, and formulating policies for widespread FOWT adoption, all of which will be accessible through the MARINEWIND WebGIS platform.

Below, the link to the Press Release, also available on the project website:

<https://mailchi.mp/wavec.org/marinewind-a-new-horizon-europe-project-to-accelerate-the-uptake-of-floating-offshore-wind-technology>

4.6 Representation at relevant stakeholder platforms and conferences

Throughout the project's lifespan, consortium partners will showcase its outcomes at external events aligned with their specialized skills and competencies. These events will take place at both the European and national levels, corresponding to the countries where the MARINEWIND Labs are situated.

During the first period of the project, UK associated partner Energy Systems Catapult (from now on, referred as CATAPULT) participated at the WindEurope Annual Event, from the 25th to 27th April 2023, in Copenhagen, Denmark, with a poster presentation titled: “MARINEWIND: Accelerating Investments in Floating Offshore Wind to Tackle European Energy Crisis”.

Figure 8 - Inès Tunga (CATAPULT) at WindEurope Annual Event announcement.

APRE also included the MARINEWIND project in its institutional event called “ASK 4 Green: An Advocacy for Social Key-instances in Green Transition¹”, official partner event to the European Green Week 2023. During this event, organised by APRE together with H2020 projects W4RES² and GREENET³ (the network of Horizon Europe Cluster 5 National Contact Points) and aimed at raising awareness about sustainability strategies and behavioural changes in society necessary for the Green Transition, the MARINEWIND project was presented by Inès Tunga from UK consortium associated partner CATAPULT. This workshop took place on June the 8th, 2023, in Brussels, and brought together policy makers, educators, and other key stakeholders. The event, that was held in hybrid mode, had an attendance of 40 participants (15 physical, 25 online).

¹ Here it is the dedicated page on APRE’s website: <https://apre.it/evento/ask-4-green-an-advocacy-for-social-key-instances-in-green-transition/>

² <https://w4res.eu/>

³ <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/cluster-5>

Figure 9 - Inès Tunga (CATAPULT) presenting MARINEWIND during the event "ASK 4 Green".

4.7 MARINEWIND Co-Creation workshops

MARINEWIND aims at organising at least 3 physical co-creation workshops in each one of the MARINEWIND Labs, in order to collect information and co-create new knowledge through a permanent dialogue with and among the MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders.

Five informative co-creation workshops have been arranged and took place during the First Period (by M12), meaning a complete first round of co-creation workshops for each of the five MARINEWIND Labs. These gatherings served as forums for connecting with vital figures for the sector, such as policymakers and public authorities. They offered project partners a platform to disseminate the most up-to-date discoveries, explore the project's advantages, and address inquiries from stakeholders.

Four cocreation workshops out of five (meaning the ones related to the Italian, Greek, Spanish and UK MARINEWIND Labs) have been recognized as official events in the framework of the “European Maritime Day 2023 – In My Country” initiative.

Figure 10 - EMD 2023 - In My Country - logo of the initiative

Below, a brief recap of the workshops that have taken place during the First Period:

- The Italian Lab 1st Co-Creation Workshop, titled “Co-creation Path to Awareness on Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)”, that took place in Bari, Italy, on the 13th of June 2023. This workshop, organized by APRE, RSE and CNR, with support from MARINEWIND Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Paola Zerilli of UoY, was held under the frame of the European Maritime Days. The event had an attendance of 33 participants.
- “Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind”, as 1st Co-creation workshop for the UK Lab, was organised by CATAPULT, with support from APRE and UoY as a side event of the “Floating Offshore Wind Conference 2023”, and took place on the 5th of October 2023, Aberdeen, UK. SENER joined the meeting as speaker, too. The event had an attendance of 14 participants of 33 registrations and eighteen were interviewed before and after it as they could not attend. It is important to point out that, being he hosting event an annual conference, the MARINEWIND project, through its UK associated partners and with the approval of the coordinator and C&D manager, will continue to participate in future editions, given the specific relevance of the topic and the success of the first synergy with the project.
- The MARINEWIND Co-creation workshop in Greece, “Co-creation Path to Awareness on Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs),” organized by Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL in collaboration with the Offshore Renewable Energy Greece event, was held on the 19th of October, 2023. The event presented the Greek market framework, existing legislations and preliminary needs, all along with valuable information from active stakeholders in the domain of Offshore Wind Technologies.
- The workshop related to the Portuguese MARINEWIND Lab, called “Co-creation Path to Awareness on Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)” and organized by WavEC together with the Administração Porto of Aveiro (Port of Aveiro), was held on the 24th of October, 2023. This event presented the MARINEWIND project to stakeholders that gathered in order to discuss a Report, prepared by the Working Group, for the planning and operationalization of electricity production centres (based on renewable energy sources of oceanic origin or location).
- The MARINEWIND 1st co-creation workshop in Spain, titled “OFFSHORE WIND IN EMPORDÀ”, was organised by SENER and held on the 25th of October, 2023, at the Casal de Pescadors in

Roses, Catalonia. It gathered over 40 experts coming from diverse groups of stakeholders, such as government, public engagement, tourism, fishing, environment, academia, industry, and research. The highlight of the day was a dynamic roundtable discussion where the organisers and the participants tackled the challenges and the opportunities in the offshore wind sector of Empordà (Northeast of Catalonia), uncovering valuable insights for MARINEWIND journey ahead.

Figure 11 – The Italian 1st Co-creation workshop in Bari

Figure 12 – The Italian 1st Co-creation workshop in Bari: participants overview.

Figure 13 – The UK 1ST Co-creation workshop in Aberdeen

Figure 14 – The Greek 1ST Co-creation workshop

Figure 15 – The Spanish 1ST Co-creation workshop

4.7.1 Event planning

The Communication and Dissemination Plan (DL5.1) for the MARINEWIND project includes a catalog of events where project partners can participate in showcasing the project. The MARINEWIND Consortium will establish and maintain an Excel document to continually identify fresh prospects for disseminating and communicating project updates, as well as to monitor project-related activities.

4.7.2 Articles in newspapers

During the Italian co-creation workshop in Bari, Riccardo Colleta from APRE and Paola Zerilli from University of York have been interviewed by “Il Nautilus” newspaper, that later published an article on the event: https://www.ilnautilus.it/porti/2023-05-25/progetto-marinewind-workshop-13-giugno-porto-di-bari_116967/

4.7.3 Performance Indicator log

Within the MARINEWIND project's Communication and Dissemination Plan (DL5.1), there is a Performance Indicator log designed as a monitoring platform to track activity progress based on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Annex I of this document contains an up-to-date iteration of this log, featuring information specific to the First Period.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In assessing the effectiveness of the MARINEWIND project's Communication and Dissemination activities during its First Period, it becomes evident that the project has adopted a diverse range of formats. These formats collectively contribute to the project's overarching goal, and there is not a single, standout method that outshines the others. Instead, it is the synergy and collaboration of these various strategies that has been the key to success.

The establishment of a distinctive brand identity, the dynamic project website, and active social media engagement have played pivotal roles in reaching and engaging stakeholders globally. Simultaneously, promotional materials, the press release, and participation in significant industry events have further enhanced the project's visibility and fostered connections with vital partners and stakeholders.

The inclusion of co-creation workshops and participation in high-impact events such as the WindEurope Annual Event and EU Green Week illustrates the project's commitment to forging meaningful relationships with policymakers and public authorities. These endeavors collectively contribute to the advancement of floating offshore wind technology systems and the resolution of Europe's energy challenges.

The credit for the success of MARINEWIND's communication and dissemination activities is undoubtedly due to the active involvement and dedication of the project's partners who have effectively disseminated the project's message. Their collective efforts have created a harmonious tapestry of communication and dissemination methods that have proven impactful. As we move forward, this collaborative approach ensures that the project is well-positioned to achieve its goals and make a lasting impact in the realm of renewable energy.

ANNEX I – PERFORMANCE INDICATOR LOG

ACTIVITY	KPI	SPECIFIC KPI	TARGET	DATE	STATUS
Brand identity: Logo & Templates	#1 brand identity kit		All Stakeholders	M1	Completed
Project Website	#1 website	>3,000 visits >27 countries reached	All Stakeholders	M6	Setup completed >1,100 visits (sessions), 25 countries reached
Social Media	#2 channels (LinkedIn and Twitter/X)	>5 social media campaigns, > 1,000 followers, > 500 posts	All Stakeholders	M6	Setup completed 130 followers, 15 posts
Flyer, Roll up and Posters	#2 flyers, #2 roll-ups, >2 posters	500 flyers distributed in at least 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs)	All Stakeholders	Version 1: M6, Version 2: M22	Flyers version 1 (English): completed and >100 distributed
Infographics	>5 infographics	#1 factsheet of the Action Plan for public acceptance, #1 Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations in at least 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs), >10 promotional banners.	All Stakeholders, in particular policymaker, civil society, businesses	M12	Under development
Multimedia Material	#1 promotional video, #2 video teasers		All Stakeholders	M12	Under development
Conferences & Events and publication	>6 speeches at events and conferences (live and online), >6 Articles in newspapers, magazines, television, or radio, >6 Press releases, #1 Final event	>6 Press releases to more than 10,000 contacts, #1 Final event to present MARINEWIND outcomes to the European Commission and other relevant stakeholders attended by at least 80 participants for the Quintuple Helix.	All Stakeholders	M12-36, Final event M34	1 Press Release completed to more than 4,000 contacts
Webinars	#2 webinars	#2 informative webinars in the 5 languages included English (for the 5 Labs) (>250 participants in total)	Policy makers and public authorities	M12-34	N/A

D5.2: Communication and Dissemination Activities

Stakeholders database	#1 database	>1,000 contacts	Partners' Networks, EU and National Projects and Initiatives, Events Participants Lists & Stakeholders Engaged	M12	>1,000 stakeholders engaged
Clustering with other projects and initiatives	>10 projects connected to MARINEWIND		EU and National Projects and Initiatives	M12-36	Under development (at M12, 5 projects)